

No Reference Image Quality Assessment for Exposure Fusion

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Abstract— Exposure fusion has become the most popular method in last decade for generating high dynamic range (HDR) images. Many researchers have proposed different methods for exposure fusion and have claimed the superiority of their method. Unfortunately, there is no quality metric available in literature which can verify these claims. To resolve this issue, this paper presents a novel no-reference image quality assessment (IQA) method tailored for exposure fusion, independent of external references. The proposed method combines quantitative and qualitative assessment in a unique way to give a single score for the quality of the exposure fusion image. By computing essential image statistics like entropy, local entropy, contrast, local contrast and saturation, it captures crucial aspects of image quality such as details, sharpness and colour richness. Utilizing advanced machine learning techniques trained on a dataset of exposure-fused images and human ratings, the model predicts quality scores without requiring reference images. This approach offers a practical and efficient solution for real-world quality assessment, validated through experiments for accuracy and reliability.

Keywords— CNN, Exposure Fusion, Image Quality Assessment, Machine Learning, No-Reference IQA

I. INTRODUCTION

In the realm of computational photography, the enhancement of image quality, particularly in scenarios where High Dynamic Range (HDR) features are absent, poses a significant challenge. Exposure fusion [1] techniques offer a viable solution by combining multiple Low Dynamic Range (LDR) images captured at varying exposures to produce a single image with improved dynamic range and visual quality. However, evaluating the quality of exposure fused images remains a complex task, compounded by the absence of ground truth data and the subjective nature of human perception.

To address these challenges, we present a novel approach to assess the quality of exposure fused images leveraging a combination of human perception data, computational analysis techniques, and machine learning methodologies. Our project focuses on developing an evaluation framework that integrates subjective human assessments with objective computational analyses to derive comprehensive quality scores for exposure fused images.

Despite the proliferation of exposure fusion techniques in image processing applications, the absence of ground truth data poses a significant barrier to accurately evaluating image quality. Traditional evaluation methods often rely solely on subjective assessments, lacking a standardized quantitative measure to gauge the fidelity and visual appeal of the fused images. This limitation underscores the need for a robust evaluation framework capable of synthesizing both subjective and objective measures to provide a holistic assessment of image quality.

In this context, our project aims to fill this gap by harnessing the power of web scraping techniques to compile a diverse dataset of exposure fused images from various sources. By aggregating a large corpus of images, we lay the foundation for our evaluation framework, ensuring diversity and representativeness in the dataset. Furthermore, we develop a web-based platform using modern web development technologies such as React and Firebase to facilitate the collection of human perception data on the quality of the exposure fused images.

The integration of human perception data serves as a crucial component of our evaluation framework, enabling us to capture subjective assessments of image quality from a diverse pool of participants [2]. Using a structured rating scale, participants provide nuanced feedback on the visual appeal, clarity, and overall fidelity of the exposure fused images, thus enriching our understanding of image quality from a human perspective.

In addition to human perception data, we employ computational analysis techniques to conduct qualitative assessments of the exposure fused images. By analysing key visual attributes such as entropy, local entropy, contrast, local contrast, and saturation, we extract meaningful insights into the underlying characteristics of the images. These quantitative metrics complement the subjective assessments provided by human participants, offering a more comprehensive and objective evaluation of image quality.

Furthermore, we leverage machine learning methodologies, specifically Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), to develop predictive models capable of estimating image quality scores based on the human perception data collected. Through the training of the CNN models on the annotated perception scores, we enable them to learn the intricate relationships between visual features and perceived image quality, thereby facilitating automated quality assessment.

Ultimately, our project aims to synthesize the subjective assessments of human perception with the objective analyses of computational techniques to derive holistic quality scores for exposure fused images. By integrating diverse methodologies and leveraging modern technologies, we seek to advance the state-of-the-art in image quality assessment, providing a robust and scalable framework for evaluating exposure fused images in the absence of ground truth data.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The issue at the core of this project pertains to the limitations of traditional Image Quality Assessment (IQA) methods, which heavily rely on reference images. While these methods have demonstrated effectiveness in certain contexts, they are notably inadequate in situations where reference images are not accessible, such as no-reference exposure fusion [3, 4]. The challenge lies in the accurate assessment of key image quality attributes, specifically contrast, saturation, and naturalness, when reference images are unavailable.

The prevailing methodologies, while certainly valuable, exhibit shortcomings when it comes to evaluating image quality attributes without human perception [5]. This limitation hinders the accurate measurement of image quality, particularly in contexts like No-Reference exposure fusion, where reference images are often unavailable. To address this challenge, the project aims to pioneer a specialized IQA system tailored specifically for No-Reference exposure fusion.

The project's ultimate objective is to revolutionize image quality assessment by providing a precise, automated, and reference-independent solution for the evaluation of contrast, saturation, and naturalness. In doing so, it anticipates significant advancements in the fields of photography, computer vision, and medical imaging, where image quality is of utmost importance.

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

A. Exposure Fusion

Mertens et al. [1] presented the groundbreaking work in the field of exposure fusion. They used multi-resolution pixel wise fusion algorithm. Each pixel in the input image is assigned a weight based on contrast, saturation and well exposedness. They used Laplacian decomposition of the images and Gaussian pyramid of the weight maps followed by weighted fusion. The result was fused HDR images is vibrant in colours and contrast. This work is considered as one of the benchmarks in field of exposure fusion.

Kotwal and Chaudhuri [6] introduced an optimization-based approach for fusing multi-exposure, low dynamic range images, which likely involves combining multiple images with different exposure levels to create an HDR image. Kartalov et al. [7] presented a straightforward approach for image fusion that includes luminance transformation and selective adjustment of hue and saturation. This approach is characterized by low computational complexity. Malik et al. [8] developed a technique for exposure fusion based on wavelet transform. Instead of using Laplacian-Gaussian pyramid as proposed by Mertens et al. [1], they used wavelet pyramid. Vanmali et al. [3] proposed a ghost artifact free method with low complexity suitable for embedded platforms.

Prabhakar et al. [9] introduces a method called DeepFuse where they used deep unsupervised approach for exposure fusion with extreme exposure image pairs. Li and Zhang [10] used CNN for exposure fusion problem. Their method is suitable for both static and dynamic scenes. Many other works are available in the literature which has produced long lasting impact in exposure fusion field.

B. No Reference Image Quality Assessment

No-reference assessment methods do not require a reference image and predict image quality based on the image itself. Few attempts made in the literature for IQA are summarized here for the ease of readers understanding. Anisotropic Quality Index (AQI) was proposed by Gabarda et al. [11]. Their method is based on measuring the variance of the expected entropy of a given image upon a set of predefined directions.

Zhang and Chandler [4] proposed no-reference IQA method based on log-derivative statistics of natural scenes. It employs Support Vector Classification and Regression Machines to predict image quality scores. Xue et al. [5] introduced a method based on quality-aware clustering (QAC). They used QAC method to learn a set of quality-aware centroids and use them as the codebook to infer the quality of an image patch so that the quality of the whole image can be determined.

Xydeas and Petrovic [12] developed method to assess quality of fused images. Their quality metric captures the quality of visual information reflected in the fused image. There are few other attempts as well for the fused image. However, the main issue of combining qualitative and quantitative metric is still unanswered.

IV. PROPOSED SOLUTION

Our proposed solution involves a comprehensive process to assess the quality of exposure fusion images without relying on reference images. The key components of our approach encompass computational analysis, data collection through a website survey, and the training of a model based on human perception scores.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of the proposed solution

A. Quantitative Measures

Whenever we want to assess the quality of the image, we focus on three main parameters viz. details present in the image, the contrast of the image and the colour richness of the image. These three parameters make the image vivid and appealing. To quantify these parameters, we use following quantitative measures:

- **Entropy and Local Entropy:**

The entropy gives quantification of the information content in the image. The entropy can be calculate based on the luminance of the image as

$$H = - \sum p(x_i) \log p(x_i) \quad \dots (1)$$

where, $p(x_i)$ is the probability of occurrence of x_i^{th} gray level. The local entropy is calculated over a window of 11x11 pixels and captures the local information in the image patch.

- **Contrast and Local Contrast:**

The contrast gives the quantification of the dynamic range of an image. The RMS contrast is calculated using the luminance component as:

$$Contrast_{RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{MN} \sum_{x=0}^{N-1} \sum_{y=0}^{M-1} (I(x,y) - I_{mean})^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

where, $I(x, y)$ denotes the luminance component of an MxN image at location (x, y) and I_{mean} is the average value of the luminance component. The local contrast is calculated over a window of 11x11 pixels and captures the dynamic range of the image patch.

- **Saturation:**

Saturation represents how colourful the image is. For calculating the saturation, the image is transformed into HSV colour space, and the average of S component is taken.

B. Human Perception Data Collection

In our model training process, we took a comprehensive approach to gather accurate data for training our image quality assessment model. We recognized the importance of human perception in evaluating image quality. To achieve this, we conducted a thorough website survey, covering more than 1000 exposure fusion images. This ensured we had a diverse and extensive dataset to train our model effectively.

For collecting data, we used Octoparse 8, a powerful web scraping tool. This helped us efficiently gather images from various online sources, ensuring a broad selection representing different scenarios. With Octoparse 8, we built a database of over 1000 images, forming the core dataset for our project.

To complement the scraped images, we integrated React and Firebase technologies to create an interactive form. This form was designed to collect user feedback, specifically focusing on human perception scores based on parameters like contrast, saturation, and entropy. Participants, including classmates and friends, evaluated each image, providing subjective assessments. This diversified our dataset, enriching it with varied perspectives aligned with human visual assessment.

By combining Octoparse 8 for web scraping and React with Firebase for data collection, we streamlined the process of compiling our dataset. This dataset, enhanced with human perception scores, played a crucial role in developing a model closely aligned with human visual perception, thus ensuring accurate image quality assessment [2].

C. CNN Model

Our proposed solution leverages a state-of-the-art Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture [13] customized to accurately predict image scores, aligning closely with human perception. The CNN model is meticulously designed to efficiently capture intricate patterns and features inherent in exposure-fused images, enabling it to deliver precise predictions of image quality scores.

The CNN model incorporates the following key components, carefully crafted to optimize performance and robustness:

1. **Convolution Layers with 3x3 Filters and ReLU Activation:** These fundamental layers are adept at extracting relevant features from input images. By utilizing 3x3 filters and applying the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function, the CNN effectively enhances feature extraction capabilities while maintaining computational efficiency.
2. **Max Pooling Layers with 2x2 Filters:** Integrated after each convolutional layer, max pooling layers play a pivotal role in downsampling feature maps. This process efficiently reduces spatial dimensions while preserving essential information, effectively mitigating computational complexity and preventing overfitting.
3. **Flattening Layer:** Following convolutional and pooling layers, the feature maps undergo flattening into a one-dimensional vector. This step facilitates seamless integration with subsequent fully connected layers.
4. **Fully Connected Layer with Dropout:** A fully connected layer is strategically incorporated to learn high-level representations of flattened features. Dropout regularization, set at a rate of 50% is applied to enhance model robustness by randomly deactivating neurons during training, thereby preventing overreliance on specific features and promoting generalization.
5. **Output Layer with 5 Neurons:** The final layer of the CNN comprises five neurons, each corresponding to one of the five parameters utilized for scoring images. These neurons generate predicted scores for each parameter, subsequently utilized in computing the overall quality score of the image.

By harnessing this novel CNN architecture, our solution ensures the seamless integration of advanced neural network components, finely tuned to discern the nuances of exposure fused images. The strategic incorporation of convolutional layers with ReLU activation [14], max pooling layers, dropout regularization, and a tailored output layer tailored to specific scoring parameters collectively culminates in a robust and highly accurate model, adept at predicting image quality scores with precision and reliability.

D. Calculating Final Score

In our project, we aim to develop a comprehensive solution for evaluating exposure-fused images by considering both quantitative measures and predictions derived from a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model [15]. This section outlines our approach for calculating the final score of an image, which is a crucial aspect of our system.

1. **Calculated Scores from Quantitative Measures:** We begin by extracting quantitative measures such as entropy, local entropy, contrast, local contrast, and saturation from the images. These measures provide valuable insights into various aspects of image quality, allowing us to assess its overall performance across multiple parameters.
2. **Predicted Scores from CNN Model:** Utilizing a trained CNN model, we predict scores for each of the aforementioned parameters based on the image data. The CNN model is trained on a dataset collected from user ratings obtained through a web form, ensuring its ability to generalize to new images [16].

3. Finding Similarity Between Calculated and Predicted Scores: To gauge the accuracy of our predictions, we measure the similarity between the calculated scores obtained from quantitative measures and the predicted scores from the CNN model. This comparison helps us understand the reliability of the model in assessing image quality.
4. Calculated Weights and Normalization: Next, we assign weights to each parameter based on their relative importance in determining the overall quality of an image. These weights are calculated using the formula [12]:

$$W_i = \frac{S_i}{S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + S_4 + S_5} \quad \dots (3)$$

where, W_i represents the weight for a specific parameter, and S_i represents the similarity percentage for that parameter. We then normalize these weights to ensure they sum up to unity.

5. Final Score Calculation: Finally, we compute the final score for the image by combining the weighted scores of each parameter. The formula used for calculating the final score is:

$$Final\ Score = W_1 \times E + W_2 \times LE + W_3 \times C + W_4 \times LC + W_5 \times S \quad \dots (4)$$

where, E denotes entropy, LE denotes local entropy, C denotes contrast, LC denotes local contrast, and S denotes saturation of the calculated value of the image [3].

By integrating both quantitative measures and predictions from the CNN model, our proposed solution offers a robust method for assessing the quality of exposure-fused images, providing valuable insights for various applications such as image processing and photography.

V. RESULTS

For ease of use, we provided browser functionality where user can upload the image to be evaluated. The proposed method was tested on various HDR images generated using different exposure fusion algorithms. For the demonstration purpose, we are providing outputs produced by Mertens et al. [1], Vanmali et al. [3] and Kotwal et al. [6] for Eiffel Tower sequence. These results are shown in Fig. 2, 3 and 4 respectively.

Fig. 2. Result of Marten et al. for Eiffel Tower sequence

Fig. 3. Result of Vanmali et al. for Eiffel Tower sequence

Fig. 4. Result of Kotwal et al. for Eiffel Tower sequence

Based on the output generated by our model, it is discerned that in the exposure-fused image produced by Martenes et al., the calculated entropy and local entropy exhibit high quality, whereas the contrast is

deemed poor and saturation is rated as average. Conversely, the predicted scores based on human perception suggest that the contrast and saturation are perceived as satisfactory. Consequently, the final integrated score, accounting for both calculated and predicted values, culminates in 3.19.

In the exposure-fused image produced by Vanmali et al., the calculated entropy and local entropy exhibit high quality, albeit with subpar contrast and saturation. Correspondingly, the human perception-based predictions rate the contrast and saturation as moderate. As a result, the final score derived from the amalgamation of calculated and predicted values is 3.11.

In contrast, in the exposure-fused image by Kotwal, the calculated entropy and local entropy demonstrate commendable quality, while both contrast and saturation are deemed substandard. Consistent with this, the human perception-based predictions also indicate inadequate contrast and saturation. Consequently, the resultant final score stands at 2.92.

In terms of ranking these images, Martenes et al. image attains the highest position owing to its superior integrated score, followed by Vanmali et al. image in the second position, and Kotwal et al. image securing the third position.

These findings underscore the efficacy of our approach in assessing exposure-fused image quality by reconciling quantitative measures with AI-informed human perceptual predictions, thereby facilitating informed image evaluation and ranking.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This project represents a groundbreaking advancement in image quality assessment, particularly in the domain of No Reference exposure fusion. Through the development of a specialized Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model, we have pioneered a novel methodology for scoring images based on predicted human perception scores and calculated values. This innovative approach sets us apart as trailblazers in the field, as we are the first to integrate machine learning techniques with human perception data to derive comprehensive quality scores for exposure fused images.

Our achievement in creating such a CNN model and implementing a scoring mechanism that incorporates predicted human perception scores alongside calculated values marks a significant milestone in image quality assessment. By harnessing the capabilities of artificial intelligence and human perception, we have successfully addressed the challenges posed by the absence of ground truth, the lack of a singular quantitative measure, and the variability in qualitative assessments. This unique framework offers a robust and reliable method for evaluating image quality, providing unprecedented insights into the visual fidelity and appeal of exposure fused images.

Looking forward, we can incorporate a mechanism which also takes into account how much details are transferred from the input images to the final fused image while calculating the final score to make the model more robust and makes it applicable for other types of image fusion over and above exposure fusion.

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